

Collaborative Statisticians as Educators: Teaching Best Data Practices to Healthcare Researchers

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Abstract

In the current "era of Big Data", clinical researchers have seen unprecedented increases in both the amount of medical data generated and recorded and the ease of access and analyzability of these data with development of new software programs. However, there are many challenges in using big data, especially from multiple sources. Thus, it is imperative for clinical researchers to have education in best practice in data management, ethics, linking, analysis, privacy, and reporting. Collaborative biostatisticians in health care are uniquely suited lead these educational efforts, due to their expertise in data issues, familiarity with data sources, and established relationships with clinical researchers. The goal of this paper was to review knowledge gaps and challenges clinicians face to utilize big data ethically and effectively for their research and patients' benefits. Another goal was to give an overview to approaches to teach data privacy and how collaborative statisticians can contribute to and shape these educational initiatives.

Key Words: education, EHR, electronic health record, big data

1. Using the Electronic Health Record for Research

The Electronic Health Record (EHR) and overall digitization of patient data has the promise of revolutionizing patient care and clinical research. EHRs are nearly ubiquitous in healthcare in the United States, with 99% of hospital reporting use of health information technology (ONC, Health IT Quick-State, 2018). Furthermore, EHRs are ever evolving, with increase breadth and depth of data; with the amount of data produced also ever increasing. With recent advancement, researchers are now able to access and utilize the computing power needed to analyze EHR data in its complexity. Over the past 20 years, there has been an exponential uptick in the number of papers using EHR data for research (Celi et al., 2016).

1.1 EHR Research and Data Flow

Using EHR data for research is a multistep process (Rahman et al., 2020), with multiple people and entities involved (Figure 1). The process of research using EHR data for research, however, begins at the same point as all clinical research, with formulating research questions. The quality of this research question will dictate the subsequent flow and success of the research process. After defining the patient cohort desired, many of the next steps in the research/data flow process are not as accessible to domain experts, and fall more within the expertise of data management, statisticians, data scientists, and informaticists. These steps involve data identification preparation pre-processing analysis and analytics, data exploration and data post processing. Following, the domain expert is heavily relied upon for interpretation and reporting. However, for more robust, clinician-

led research to be successful, there is a need to amplify the interactions and contributions of clinician scientists through the process (Rahman et al., 2020).

Figure 1: General Overview of Electronic Health Record Data and Research Flow.

1.2 Research Uses of EHR

EHR can be both a primary and secondary data source for research. Use of EHRs for observational studies is probably its most common and widely accepted use. EHRs support a range of these types of studies including studies involving health care and drug utilization, epidemiological studies, natural history studies, and studies of risk factors for health outcome (Cowie et al., 2017). Modern EHRs also minimize the need for duplicate data (registries) and contain longitudinal data on patients. Additionally, depending on the design and quality of a given HER, these data can be linked to other data sources (e.g., Medicare) as we data collected in other sectors (e.g., housing, education) (Cowie et al., 2017)

There is growing recognition that EHRs can be used to enhance clinical research, particularly prospective research, but it still can be limited even though much of the data collected overlaps with data collected for clinical research (Cowie et al., 2017). Most commonly, EHRs are used for feasibility processes, i.e. identifying pools of patients, and supporting patient recruitment, and can be used to generate lists of patients who may be eligible for a study. However, depending on HER data quality, this approach can produce incomplete data and miss eligible patients. Additionally, EHRs can facilitate and streamline pre-screening for exclusion and inclusion criteria and provide information and support for point of care randomization (Cowie et al., 2017). EHR data has the potential to also be a primary source for study data; for example, it can be a more accurate a robust resource for patient comorbidity and medication data. Further, especially for randomized control trials, EHRs can be useful in straining serious adverse events in patients, particularly in the long term (Cowie et al., 2017). Finally, EHRs align well with shift towards pragmatic trials, which focus on context of routine care and reduction of trial specific visits (Cowie et al., 2017). Pragmatic studies can then have additional modules for data not in the EHR (e.g. specific patient reported or study specific outcomes).

Figure 2: Examples of Research Uses of Electronic Health Record Data

2. Challenges to Using the Electronic Health Record for Research

2.1 Research as a Secondary Use

A major challenge with using EHR data for research is that research is not the primary use of EHR data. Its intended use is for patient care and was specifically designed with billing concerns in mind. The organization of EHR data is focused on diagnostics and procedure codes, without consideration of complex and dynamic uses of EHR data for research and other purposes (Kim et al., 2019; Holmes et al., 2021).

2.1.1 Structured vs Unstructured Data

The EHR contains multiple formats of data, which are often incompatible, at least in their raw form (Kim et al., 2019). There are two main categories of data produced by the EHR: structures and unstructured. Structured data uses codes from predefined clinical concepts (e.g., diagnoses, procedures). Structured data can also include demographic data commonly used in research, including gender/sex, race, insurance types, etc. Additionally, clinical information that can be quantitatively summarized and entered in the EHR (e.g., blood pressure, laboratory results, clinical questionnaires) would also be considered structured. Structured formats can be easily de-identified and entered into databases, with few steps needed before being ready for data analysis (Ford et al., 2020).

Unstructured data, on the other hand, is much more variable and had no defined formatting. This data can include free text, clinical notes, images, and audio files (Ford et al., 2020). In some cases, this data can be machine readable, but in other cases it is not. Unstructured data requires considerable pre-processing prior to analysis. Even though it is more difficult to manage and analyze, unstructured data can contain valuable, substantive information for research; information and nuance that could be missed if research relies solely on structured data analysis (Ford et al., 2020). Fortunately, data science advancements, including natural

language processing, is providing robust technique to aid the preprocessing and use of unstructured EHR data for research (Kim et al., 2019).

Figure 3: Examples of Structured and Unstructured Data

2.1.2 Issues with Common Data Types

As reviewed by Pollard et al. (2016) different data types and sources can have their own specific issues. For example, demographic data, especially in combination with other variables, can contain highly sensitive information that would require careful de-identification and data quality for some demographic fields, such as ethnicity, may be overall poor (Pollard et al., 2016). Unstructured data such as radiographic images may contain direct patient identifies (e.g., names, dates of procedures). Though seemingly objective, diagnostic and procedure codes can be biased. Often, these codes are applied after retrospective review of patient chart and can be subject to coder bias. Additionally, there may be institutional, or insurance-related limitations on what codes can be applied. Finally, clinic notes can contain typographical errors, abbreviations, and non-standard acronyms that can delay data processing (Pollard et al., 2016).

2.2 Specific Barriers to Using EHR

Cowie et al. (2017) and Kim et al. (2019) outline multiple barriers to using EHR data: data quality and validation, complete data capture, time access, heterogeneity, security and privacy, and system knowledge. Data quality and validation is of vital importance in using EHR data for research. Coding error and inaccurate information will negatively affect the integrity and validity of research studies using this data. Furthermore, if there is any systematic bias in these coding areas, this could cause selection bias in studies, especially if coding error involve inclusion criteria such as diagnostic or procedure codes, or demographic data (Cowie et al., 2017). Complete data capture is another necessary component of the use of EHR data for research. In particular, differential provider reporting can affect variables of interest to research. Furthermore, if there is differential longitudinal data capture for patients, certain endpoints (e.g., adverse events, mortality) may not be reliable (Cowie et al., 2017). Finally, one challenge area where collaborative statisticians can specifically provide insight is system knowledge. Challenges with using EHR can arise from a lack of knowledge about how the EHR is constructed as well as the data limitations that exist with using EHR data for research (Cowie et al., 2017).

3. Education on Use of Electronic Health Record Data for Research

3.1 Education for Clinical Researchers

The creation, growth, and access to EHR and other “big data” as greatly outpaced clinical training in this area. Moreover, training in EHR tends to focus on patient/clinical use, rather than research use, with research aspects an issue deemphasized or not introduced until much later in training (Kim et al., 2019). Issues important to research uses of EHR data, including secondary extraction, data aggregations, and data appraisal are either not introduced or oversimplified (Rajaram et al., 2020). Finally, as noted by Rajaram et al. (2020), studies on EHR education had varying levels of robust statistical and research methodology employed.

Beyond education in research us of EHR data, the literature demonstrates overall deficits in clinical research knowledge and competency in statistical methods needed for clinical research (Windish et al., 2007). There are many issues related to this deficit including

overall lack of priority, with research concepts not emphasized in core competency and competing demands on clinical researchers' time. Moreover, courses on research and statistical methods are often elective and/or focus mainly on critical appraisal, via journal clubs or evidence-based medicine seminars, with little to no exposure to data-related concepts (Windish et al., 2007; MacDougall et al., 2020). Finally, a major issue noted in the literature is an over lack of clinical research with appropriate training to teach and design curricula on research and data concepts (Celi et al., 2016), this is where collaborative statisticians in the health sciences can have a substantial impact. By not adequately teaching practice research skills and data management concepts, the current education paradigm is leaving today's clinical researchers unprepared for the "big data" era (Celi et al., 2016).

3.2 Statistician-Led Educational Approaches to Using EHR for Research

Collaborative statisticians in the health sciences are uniquely suited to address gaps in clinical research statistical knowledge to better prepare them for using "big data," the EHR, for research. Collaborative biostatisticians have the needs technical experience, with continual training, and are well versed in problems and challenges working with large data sets. Moreover, collaborative biostatisticians who work in the health science are experienced in working in multidisciplinary teams, are experts in communicating complex statistical topics to clinicians, and already understand basic clinical terminology to support clinical research collaborators in their use of HER data for research.

3.2.1 Teach Clinical Informatics Concepts throughout Medical Education

Clinical informatics concepts should be included in curricula early on in medical training, and revisited and reviewed throughout a clinical researcher's career. Clinical informatics curricula should introduce how clinical researchers can access the EHR and other data resources and how to specifically utilizes these resources for research (Zainal et al., 2023). In a study by Chen et al. (2022), medical students reported one of the most useful modules in their clinical informatics enrichment course was practicums on the EHR, in which student had the opportunity for hands-on EHR data experiences. Next, it is important to introduce analytics concepts, both without and without coding, so that clinical researchers can understand the approaches to analyzing "big data." In terms of analytics, courses can be flexible and give the option of more advanced analytics training if desired. The important goal is to familiarize clinical researchers with analytic terminology so that they can better communicate with collaborators. Finally, clinical informatics courses should also review data management concerns, security and privacy issues, and ethic of using the EHR for research purposes. Collaborative biostatisticians in the health science are in a position to advocate for more emphasis on clinical informatics in medical training, and incorporation of clinical informatics content in core competencies (Rajaram et al., 2020; Zainal et al., 2023).

3.2.2 Strengthen Statistical and Data Management Foundations

In addition to clinical informatics training, collaborative biostatistician in the health sciences should take an active role in improving basic data and statistical skills and understanding in clinical researchers. These are foundation topics underlying clinical informatics. In a study by Chen et al (2022) assessing a clinical informatics course for medical students, students were asked to rank concepts and modules reviewed in terms of usefulness and importance. Foundational topics, including data extraction, cleaning, and quality checking were ranked highest. More advanced clinical informatics topics (e.g., machine learning) were though to be interesting to the students, however, were not considered a priority. Other studies have also shown that foundational skills including

graphical representation of the data and arranging data in spreadsheets and ranked as some of the most important statistical competencies for clinical researchers (MacDougall et al., 2020). Additionally, in the course run by Chen et al. (2020) student interest increased when delivery was tailored to the content, including using hands on workshops, live demonstrations, and expert panels. The teaching of data and research concepts needs to consider different backgrounds of clinical learners as well as have thoughtful presentation of concepts, using useful examples and methods for learning. Finally, a goal of both basic data/research and clinic informatics courses should be understanding and engagement, not 100% mastery. Collaborative biostatisticians should ensure that such courses be offered in a low stakes manner (e.g., pass/fail).

3.2.3 Foster Cross-Disciplinary Collaborations

Finally, beyond curricular changes, collaborative biostatisticians can also help clinical research foster a multidisciplinary, collaborative mindset and approach so they can successfully conduct clinical studies using the EHR and other “big data” sources. With the increasing complexity of EHR and analytical approaches using EHR data, team science needs to be encouraged and emphasized (Celi et al., 2016). Building a multidisciplinary culture takes time and there are approaches that can be used. For example, medical schools and departments can host cross-disciplinary journal clubs, with a special emphasis on using EHR data. These journal clubs can allow all collaborative to gain different perspectives on using EHR for research. Likewise, medical schools can maintain online platforms for clinicians and data scientists to interact, even asynchronously. This can facilitate when clinical researchers have a general question, are seeking training/resources, or want to start a collaboration. There are other innovations emerging to foster cross-disciplinary relationship, including “datathons,” a term coined via work by Aboab et al. (2016). In their first datathon, Aboab et al. invited a variety of experts, including clinical researchers, statisticians, and data scientists, for a multi-day period, with access to a “big data” source. They then form multidisciplinary teams to generate ideas and produce clinical research. Another goal of Aboab et al. (2016) was to create teams that would potentially continue these collaborations after their event. These events could be especially useful for researchers in more isolated departments and health science centers.

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